

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE COMPOSITION OF NUTS OF THE KYRGYZ REPUBLIC

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139795>

Aksupova A.,
PhD, professor

Belekova G.,
professor

Aksupova A.

*Researchers of LLC "Educational and Consulting Center "Test-Expertise",
Kyrgyz Republic, 720044, Junusaliev str.183, # 51, Bishkek*

Abstract

The article presents the results of studies of the composition of nuts products from south regions of the Kyrgyz Republic - Osh and Jalal- Abad regions. These studies are aimed at creating a database on the composition of food products in the Kyrgyz Republic. This study was carried out with the support of the "Establishment of Asian Food Composition Database -" Asian Food and Agriculture Cooperation Initiative (AFACI), Rural Development Administration, Republic of Korea. Testing of food products was carried out by the Educational and Consulting Center "Test-Expertise" in the Testing Laboratory of Food and Agricultural Products of the CSM under the Ministry of Economy of the Kyrgyz Republic

The results of a comparative analysis of the chemical and mineral composition of the objects of study are presented.

Keywords: nuts, chemical and mineral composition

Introduction

Nuts are enjoying increasing consumer popularity all over the world. The most popular among consumers are peanuts, walnuts, pistachios, almonds, cashews, hazelnuts, pecans, pine nuts and Brazil nuts [1,2,3,4].

Nuts are a group of high-calorie nutritious foods with a rich composition and high content of antioxidants. Due to the emergence of studies proving the benefits of nut consumption, the nut production industry has become one of the most effective international types of business. The global trend associated with an increase in the consumption of natural foods rich in high-grade proteins and vegetable fats with a high content of polyunsaturated fatty acids, as well as the results of new studies on the benefits of nuts obtained at leading universities in the world, led to an increase in the consumption of nuts [5].

Nuts by their nutritional value can be attributed to natural bioconcentrates. Nuts are a group of high-calorie nutritious foods with a rich composition and high content of antioxidants. Antioxidants are crucial for health. Scientists believe that they control the aging process by fighting free radicals. The composition of nuts includes several unique and very powerful antioxidants that are not found in other products. Almost 90% of these elements are concentrated in the skin of fruits. The high content of polyphenolic substances reduces the activity of oxidative processes. The results of one of the studies confirmed that the antioxidants contained in nuts prevent liver damage as a result of chemical poisoning.

With a low moisture content, nuts have a unique complex of micro- and macronutrients. Since ancient times, it has been believed that nuts activate physical and mental activity, promote longevity, and provide energy balance in the human body. The dissemination of

the results of new studies on the benefits of nuts obtained at leading universities in the world contributes to an increase in the consumption of nuts.

Walnuts (*Juglans regia* L.) are one of the most popular types of nuts. Walnuts are also of interest to the Kyrgyz Republic economy – walnuts are a source of useful plant oil, they can be consumed in their natural form, they can be used as components of other products, including functional ones, due to the high content of unsaturated fats, proteins, vitamins and minerals. Walnuts are a natural healthy nutrient-rich food.

Peanuts are one of the most affordable and popular nuts at the moment. Thanks to the rich composition of useful elements, peanuts help restore cells, strengthen immunity, improve performance, strengthen blood vessels, and prevent the negative effects of stress, it also helps the body fight free radicals, improves brain function, memory, has a positive effect on the heart, blood pressure and metabolism.

Pistachios occupy a special place among nuts. They contain a large amount of useful substances and this has a positive effect on human health. These nuts affect the restoration of the psycho-emotional background, the cardiovascular system, have a tonic and antioxidant effect on the body. Pistachios are recommended for people who have intense physical and mental stress. Also, these green nuts are shown to patients who have recently had an illness. Due to the content of fatty acids, this product helps to burn "bad" cholesterol, thereby preventing the development of heart attacks and atherosclerosis. Magnesium and potassium, which are part of pistachios, strengthen the walls of blood vessels and restore a rapid heartbeat. These miracle nuts contain lutein, which is good for the eyes. This carotenoid increases visual acuity and is a good prevention to promote eye health.

The use of pistachios in medicine

Since pistachios have a huge amount of useful substances, they are actively used in medicine. For example, peeled fruits are used for digestive disorders, help to get rid of anemia due to the content of vitamin B6, help with bronchitis, having an antitussive effect. This nut is rich in proteins, mono-saturated fats and carbohydrates, which remove toxins, toxins and purify the blood, which prevents the appearance of diabetes.

It is also necessary to pay special attention to pistachio oil, which is obtained from fruits by cold pressing. It contains oleic acid, vitamins A, B and E. The oil is easily distributed over the skin, perfectly absorbed and strengthens its protective functions.

Nuts occupy a special niche among physiologically active, balanced foods. At the same time, the chemical composition of nut crops varies significantly depending on the place and conditions of growth, cultivation technology (on irrigated or non-irrigated areas), harvest time, drying methods, storage conditions and botanical varieties [6].

Based on this, special attention should be paid to increasing the area of cultivation, storage, transportation and sale of nuts and their use in the food industry, as well as to make a worthy contribution to the economy of Kyrgyzstan. In accordance with the above, nut producers are faced with the task of conducting studies of nuts on the content of basic nutrients, amino acid

composition and minerals, nutritional and biological value.

Main part

The study of the chemical composition of food products, including nuts, the most useful food products, is one of the most important tasks of nutrition science. Knowledge about the composition of food products is necessary for nutrition specialists, nutritionists to assess the nutritional status of the population, planning the production and creation of new food products, developing nutrition recommendations, menu calculations, etc.

The purpose of this work is a comprehensive study on the content of proteins, fats, moisture, as well as amino acid and fatty acid composition of the studied nuts from peeled pistachios, walnut kernels, peanut kernels of Osh and Jalal-Abad regions of Kyrgyzstan.

To study the composition of peeled pistachios, walnut kernels, peanut kernels, standard test methods were used for the mineral composition, an optical emission spectrometer was used with a wide spectrum of mineral composition determination and very high reliability, high accuracy of the detection limit, the fatty acid composition was determined by gas chromatographic analysis, the amino acid composition was studied on a liquid amino acid analyzer. The protein was determined by the Kjeldahl method, the fat content by the Soxhlet method [7-13]. The research results of testing are presented in tables 1,2,3,4,5.

Table 1

Chemical composition of different products by regions of the Kyrgyz Republic

#	Name of nuts	Ash content, %	Mass fraction of moisture, %	Mass fraction of protein, %	Mass fraction of fat, %
Jalal-Abad region					
24	Peeled pistachios	2,83	4,3±1,01	27,5±1,1	38,4±0,15
Osh region					
25	Walnut kernels	2,18	3,5±1,01	19,2±0,87	65,2±0,15
26	Peanut kernels	2,47	4,0±1,01	33,6±0,87	62,7±0,15

The results of the research show that the moisture content and are within acceptable regulatory limits. The ash content index in the nuts under study corresponds to the generally accepted reference data and is within the same order and is equal to the ash content from 2.0% to 2.8%., which indicates their mineral value.

According to the content of the mass fraction of fat, the kernels of walnuts and peanuts turned out to be a more fat-containing product (65,2 %±0,15%, 62,7%±0,15%), unlike peeled pistachios (38.4 ± 0.15). Reference indicators correspond to the content range up to 45.2-60.7%. The use of these products has a beneficial effect on the body and reduces the factors of cardiovascular diseases. They help in reducing the risk factors for the development of metabolic syndrome, such as high blood pressure and cholesterol levels.

In terms of ash content, discrepancies with reference data are insignificant and amount to 0.13-0.18%.

The existing discrepancies with the reference data on the content of the main nutrients in nuts confirm the need to conduct studies of their composition in the Kyrgyz Republic, since the natural and climatic conditions of the growing regions play an important role in the formation of the composition.

This statement is confirmed by the results of a study of the mineral composition of nuts grown in two regions of the Kyrgyz Republic – Osh and Jalal-Abad

regions. In terms of the quantitative content of all minerals, especially Ca, Na (with the exception of walnut kernels), K, P, Mg, Mn, Zn, Cu, Fe, B, the Jalal-Abad region significantly exceeds the Osh region. This indicates more favorable cultivation conditions in this region (Table 2).

The analysis of the results of studies of the mineral composition of the nuts under study for 19 macro- and microelements was carried out for pistachios and peanut walnut kernels. The study of the quantitative content of such basic macronutrients as Ca, Na shows that the indicators are several times higher than the reference data. The K content in walnut kernels is 6399.3 mg / mg, which is five times more than the need, and in peeled pistachios it exceeds 8 times. The content of P, Mn, Zn in these products is 10-20 times higher than the standard generally accepted indicators. Nuts are rich in macro- and microelements, especially calcium, magnesium, phosphorus and potassium. Such a chemical composition of nut fruits makes them a full-fledged food product, which allows providing the human body with substances necessary for vital activity. According to the Se content in the prototype, it turned out to be 2-3 times less than the reference indicator. The iron content in pistachios and nuts is several times higher in terms of the amount in them compared to reference data. The content of I, B, Li is

several times higher than the control values. The Co content is 0.002 mg/kg, which is significantly less than the reference data of 7.3 mg. It is obvious that such a difference between experimental and reference data is

facilitated by the influence of natural and climatic conditions and the composition of the soil on which nut trees are grown.

Table 2.

Mineral composition of the studied types of nuts by regions of the Kyrgyz Republic.																			
Osh region																			
Mineral name	Content, mg/kg																		
	Ca	Na	K	P	Mn	Zn	Se	Cu	Fe	I	B	Li	Al	Mg	V	Ni	Co	Cr	Sn
Jalal-Abad region																			
Pistachios	1208,9	6534,7	5216,4	8945,5	10,5	33,9	1,02	7,72	26,7	1,83	16,09	0,45	9,51	963,8	0,05	1,51	0,03	0,80	1,75
Walnut kernels	587,2	66,1	3527,3	6399,31	17,4	40,65	5,55	14,71	19,38	2,47	5,87	0,02	1,95	256,6	0,003	0,49	0,002	0,37	0,16

Fig. 1. clearly shows the maximum content of Na, Ca, K, P, Zn in pistachio nuts compared to the kernels of peanuts and walnuts. At the same time, the content of these elements is in a minimum amount in peanuts.

The results of studies of the amino acid and fatty acid composition of peanut kernels from the Osh region; peeled pistachios and walnut kernels from the Jalal-Abad region are presented in Tables 3, 4, 5.

Amino acids play an important role in human life. As is known, the biological value of the product is determined by the amino acid composition, which characterizes its overall nutritional value in metabolism in the human body.

The data obtained as a result of laboratory tests of the amino acid and fatty acid composition of some

types of nuts allowed us to compile the following analytical information. The test results are presented in Table 3, 4.

Based on the data obtained, it can be assumed that by the total content, by the quantitative content of essential and interchangeable amino acids (defined in the samples), all types of nuts are full-fledged sources of proteins that the human body regularly needs.

In all these types of nuts, amino acids necessary for the human body are determined, which gives a well-founded idea of the nutritional and biological value of products.

Table 3

Results of the study of the amino acid composition of nuts growing in the regions of the Kyrgyz Republic

№	Name of indicators, units of measurement	Types of nuts		
		Peanut kernels	Walnut kernels	Pistachios
		Osh region	Jalal Abad region	
Amino acid composition, mg/100 g:				
1	Aspartic acid	2633,7	1198	1897,2
2	Glutamic acid	4980,2	3039,2	3994,7
3	Serine	1306,9	692,2	1285,9
4	Histidine	356,4	397,1	527
5	Glycine	1505	980,4	1001,3
6	Threonine	732,7	577,5	706,2
7	Arginine	2950,5	2242,2	2118,5
8	Alanine	1059,4	284,3	959,1
9	Tyrosine	1039,6	571,6	432,1
10	Cysteine	326,7	117,6	379,4
11	Valine	1014,9	954,9	1296,4
12	Methionine	287,1	300	358,4
13	Tryptophan	277,2	171,6	284,6
14	Phenylalanine	1326,7	752	1106,7
15	Isoleucine	891,1	752	938,1
16	Leucine	1742,6	1203,9	1623,2
17	Lysine	930,7	432,4	1201,6
18	Proline	1188,1	693,1	853,7

Fig.2. Chart of amino acid composition, mg/100g.

1. Peeled pistachios: The amino acid composition of the proteins of these nuts is complete. These proteins contain all the essential amino acids that the human body must receive daily to build its protein complexes. The content of such essential amino acids as tryptophan, threonine, lysine in pistachios is 2192.4 g per 100 g of nuts, which fully provides the daily norm for an adult. Among the amino acids in 100 g of nuts, threonine, tryptophan and lysine contain the most, respectively 119%, 108% and 71% of the daily requirement. Methionine contains only 358.4 g, which is 26% of the daily dose.

2. Walnut kernels: The amino acid composition of walnut kernels is represented by the following essential amino acids, such as threonine, tryptophan, arginine, phenylalanine, which have 3818 g in 100 g of nuts and contain respectively 106%, 60%, 46%, 36% from the daily requirement rate. Methionine contains 300 g, which is 18% of the required daily requirement.

3. Peanut kernels: The biological value of peanut proteins is related to the content of essential amino acids in them, which are necessary for human life, but cannot be synthesized by the body itself. The amino acid composition of peanut protein is mainly represented by amino acids such as threonine, tryptophan, phenylalanine, arginine, leucine, which contain 2636.6 g per 100g and make up 133%, 114%, 67%, respectively, of the required daily dose. Methionine contains 287.1 g, which is 22% of the required daily requirement. Thanks to tryptophan, an amino acid from which serotonin is synthesized, peanuts not only improves mood, but also copes with depressive states and stress.

The results of the fatty acid composition of nuts characterize the degree of biological value of the product in combination with the content of fat, proteins, amino acids and their digestibility in the human body. Therefore, the study of this indicator in different types of nuts is of great practical and scientific and methodological importance, Table 4, 5.

Table 4

Results of the study of the fatty acid composition of nuts growing in the regions of the Kyrgyz Republic

Saturated fatty acids, %	Peanut kernels	Walnut kernels	Pistachios
	16,657	8,208	10,724
C10:0 caprine	-	-	0,06
C14:0 myristic	0,046	0,06	0,181
C15:0 pentadecane	0,016	0,034	0,042
C16:0 palmitic	11,517	5,327	8,962
C17:0 margarine	0,063	0,032	0,021
C18:0 stearic	2,177	2,604	1,393
C20:0 arachinic	0,168	0,128	-
C23:0 tricosanic	-	-	0,051
C24:0 lignoceric acid	-	-	0,008
Monounsaturated fatty acids, %	Peanut kernels	Walnut kernels	Pistachios
	39,459	23,246	60,06
C16:1(cis-9) palmitoleic	0,046	0,064	0,706
C15:1 (cis-10) pentadecenoic	-	0,017	-
C17:1 (cis-10) margarinoic	0,024	0,014	0,044
C18:1 (cis-9) oleic	38,098	23,044	58,983
C20:1 (cis-11) eicosenoic	1,292	0,107	0,32
C24:1 (cis-15) selacholic	-	-	0,007
Polyunsaturated fatty acids, %	Peanut kernels	Walnut kernels	Pistachios
	43,883	68,546	29,216
C18:2n6c linoleic	42,716	56,044	28,789
C18:3n6 Y-linolenic	0,088	12,501	0,379
C20:3n6c (cis-8, 11, 14) eicosatrienoic	1,022	-	-
C20:4n6 arachidonic	0,058	-	-
C20:5n3 eicosapentaenoic	-	-	0,049

The analysis of the obtained results of the fatty acid composition of nuts showed the following:

In samples of all types of nuts, the following were determined: the total content of saturated fatty acids (PUFA) with the identification of up to 8 of them; monounsaturated fatty acids (MNFA), with the identification of 5 of them; polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), with the identification of 3 names, Fig. 3, 4,

In samples of all types of nuts, the following was determined: the total content of saturated fatty acids (PUFA) with the identification of up to 8 of them; monounsaturated fatty acids (MUNFA) with the identification of 5 of them; polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) with the identification of 3 names, Fig. 3. in walnut kernels totaled 8,208% and determined 7 saturated fatty acids. The content of palmitic acid is 5.327%, stearic acid is 2.604%, arachinic acid is 0.128%, the rest have the same order of indicators. The content (NLC) in the experimental data exceeds the reference need for them by 15-20%.

The peanut kernels totaled 16.657% and 7 saturated fatty acids were determined. The content of palmitic acid is 11.517%, tricosan 2.671% and stearic

2.177%, arachin 0.168%, the rest (NLC) have indicators of the same order.

- Monounsaturated fatty acids (MUNFA)

● in pistachios peeled in total amounted to 60.06% and were determined by 5 names of MNFA. The content of oleic acid is 58.983%, palmitoleic acid is 0.706% and selacholic acid has the lowest content of 0.007%. When compared with reference data, the content of experimental indicators exceeds the need for peeled pistachios by 15-20%.

Monounsaturated fats found in peeled pistachios reduce the risk of heart disease and even heart attack.

The walnut kernels totaled 23.246% and identified 5 names of MUNFA. The highest content of oleic acid leaves 23.044%, the remaining names have indicators of the same order.

Content of experienced показателей на 15% выше, чем справочные показатели.

in the kernels, the peanut content was 39.459% and 4 names of MUNFA were identified. The content of oleic acid is 38,098%. The content of eicosenic acid was 1.022%/

Polyunsaturated fatty acids:

● in the peeled pistachios totaled 29.216% and identified

4 names, of which 28.789% linoleic acid has a high index. The remaining acids have indicators of the same order.

● in walnut kernels, a total of 68.546% were made up and 2 names of MUNFA were identified. Linoleic acid has the highest index. Its content is 56.044%, and linolenic acid has indicators of 12.501%.

● there were identified a total of 68.546% in walnut kernels, and 2 names of MUNFA were identified. Linoleic acid has the highest index. Its content is 56.044%, and linolenic acid has indicators of 12.501%.

In general, of the identified polyunsaturated fatty acids in the kernels of nuts, the content of C18:2p6c linoleic acid is much higher than other identified fatty acids, and walnut kernels contain the greatest amount of this acid. When comparing the indicators with reference indicators, it is obvious that the content of

polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) in the experimental indicators is several times higher than the needs. Based on this, it can be concluded that when using peeled pistachios, walnut kernels and peanut kernels, certain indicators must be observed, taking into account the recommendations for their use and their balance in the body, as well as in what form they should be consumed.

Based on the above, it can be noted that physico-chemical indicators can vary not only depending on environmental conditions, climate, soil, but also on the variety. The high content of fats, proteins, etc. indicates the nutritional value of nuts, their competitiveness, and they can also be used in the development of new functional products for schoolchildren, athletes, women and the elderly with the content of high-calorie and full-fledged foods rich in minerals.

References:

1. Martovshuk, V. I. Influence of roasting technology on the quality of hazelnut kernels / V. I. Martovshuk [et al.] // *Izvestia of higher educational institutions. Food technology.* – 2016. – № 1 (349). – Pp. 50-53.
2. Orlova, O. Yu. Modern aspects of the use of walnut fruits in the technology of functional food products / O. Yu. Orlova [et al.] // *Modern aspects of the use of renewable natural resources in the technology of functional and specialized food products: A collective monograph.* – St. Petersburg : Publishing house "LEM", 2012. – 254 p.
3. Страхова, С. А. Влияние состава, зрелости и режима хранения на качество грецкого ореха : дис. ... учен. степ. канд. техн. наук / С. А. Страхова. – М., 1966. – 157 с.
4. Chen, B. Physical Structures in Soybean Oil and Their Impact on Lipid Oxidation / B. Chen [etal.] // *J. Agric. Food Chem.* – 2010. – Vol. 58, № 22. – P. 11993–11999.
5. Church, I. J. Modified atmosphere packaging technology: A review / I. J. Church, A. L. Parsons // *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture.* – 1995. – Vol. 67, № 2. – P. 143–152.
6. Pegg, R. B. Measurement of Primary Lipid Oxidation Products. *Current Protocols in Food Analytical Chemistry* / R. B. Pegg. – 2001. – 198 p.
7. GOST 3626-73. Method for determining the mass fraction of moisture in dairy products. // *Standartinform.-2009.-Vol.50.*
8. GOST 23327-98. Method for determining the mass fraction of protein in dairy products on the device Keltran UK-4005 // *Standartinform.-2009.-Vol.50.*
9. GOST 9793-2016. Method for determining the mass fraction of moisture in meat products // *Standartinform.-2016.-Vol.7*
10. GOST 25011-2017. Method for determining the mass fraction of protein in meat products on the device Keltran UK-4005 // *Standartinform.-2016.-Vol.13*
11. GOST 23042-2015. Method for determining the mass fraction of the mass fraction of fat in meat products on the Soxlet apparatus // *Standartinform.-2015.-Vol.8.*
12. GOST 31727-2012. Method for determining the mass fraction of the mass fraction of ash. // *Standartinform.-2015.-Vol.7*
13. GOST 30538-97. Determination of mineral substances by the NPP-ISP method on the ICAP 6000/7000/PRO spectrometer No. 51/21 // *Standartinform.-2010.-Vol.27*